

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Laboratory Processing of Human and Animal Stool samples	
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Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes after initial pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable to the processing of human and animal stool samples from households included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL E coli (ESBL-E) and ESBL K pneumoniae (ESBL-K) is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

These methods will be used to process human and animal stool samples received into the laboratory from the DRUM study.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of human and animal stool, and environmental samples in according to Sample Collection SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
 - Inform Study Laboratory Technicians of sample arrival
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
 - Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception
 - Double-check correct sample labelling
 - Processing stool samples in accordance with this SOP

- Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. Procedure

4.1 Materials needed

Gloves

Electronic scales

Microbiological loops

Buffered Peptone Water (at room temperature)

Sterile 30ml Containers (or autoclavable 30ml glass vials)

Sterile 10ul Bacterial loops

Cryovials

Pipette, 1000ul & 200ul pipette tips

30ml falcon tube or small measuring cylinder

Permanent Marker (or labels)

4.2 Storage conditions

All reagents should be stored as per the instructions of the manufacturer

4.3. Test Procedure – Processing Human and Animal Stool Samples

Buffered Peptone Water (at room temperature)

Sterile 30ml Containers (or autoclavable 30ml glass vials)

Sterile 10ul Bacterial loops

1000ul pipette tips and pipettes

Cryovials

Gloves

Fine marker

30ml falcon tube or small measuring cylinder

1. Samples will arrive in 30ml polypropylene stool container or rectal swab. For stool in polypropylene containers take a 10ul loop of fresh stool and place in a new sterile container containing 10ml of BPW (room temperature), ensuring the stool is dispersed within the liquid.
2. Incubate the container in an aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
3. With the remaining stool sample transfer 1.8ml (of fresh stool) into a 1.8ml cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on stool box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
4. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on stool box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
5. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
6. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.4 Test Procedure – Processing of Human and Animal Stool Swabs

Buffered Peptone Water (at room temperature)

1.8ml cryovial

Sterile 30ml Container (or autoclavable 30ml glass vials)

Buffered peptone water

1000ul pipette tips

200ul pipette tips

Gloves

Scissors

30ml falcon tube or small measuring cylinder

1. For participants unable to provide a stool sample and poultry samples, two rectal swabs will be taken instead of fresh stool samples, and these swabs should arrive at the laboratory together.
2. Both of these swabs should be placed into a stool collection pot / universal container, containing 5ml of BPW, and vortexed for 30s to remove bacterial material. The swabs can then be discarded
3. 1.8ml of BPW should be transferred to a 1.8ml cryovial for storage at -80°C.
4. A further 5ml of BPW can be added to the container to create a total volume of ~8ml.
5. Incubate the container in aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
6. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on stool box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
7. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
8. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.5. Buffered Peptone Water (BPW)

1. Weigh **20 grams** of powder and disperse in 1L of deionised water
2. Mix to dissolve and then distribute into bottles
3. Sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.

Appearance: Pale, straw, clear liquid

pH: 7.2 ±0.2

Minimum Q. C. organisms: E. coli WDCM 00090

Storage of Prepared Medium: Capped container – up to 3 months at 15-20°C in the dark.

Inoculation: Add 25 grams of a sample to 225ml of BPW and homogenise

Incubation: Aerobically at 37°C for 18-24hrs

5. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines